

Gesture Recognition Using MediaPipe and OpenCV

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we try to recreate a simple gesture-recognition model attached to a camera that would then be used to interact with a computer such as clicking and scrolling on websites. In order to do this, we used mediapipe's basic online gesture recognition AI and colab's capture video code in order to capture images that would then be fed into the model to determine the gesture. Determining the gesture was hard for the AI, especially if the lighting or camera angle was off even a tiny bit. A way of interacting with websites has not been made due to the complications of implementing a way to do that. Overall, the model had a somewhat low accuracy that could intervene in interacting with computers that could cause it to do the wrong actions. In the future, better algorithms or data could be used to deal with these limitations.

KEYWORDS

AI, Computer Vision, Gesture Recognition

1 INTRODUCTION

During this time of major technological improvements, computers have done exceptionally well at doing what humans could do, such as detecting objects and movements through a frame captured by a camera. Computer vision is where AI is used to see the world and can understand the real world like humans do. Computer vision is especially helpful when dealing with facial recognition for phones, object detection for cars, and more. However, there are many limitations to computer vision such as the environment the camera is used in, the requirement of using large amounts of data to train the AI, the use for large computational power, privacy, etc. Using MediaPipe's basic AI gesture recognition model, we could capture common gestures in order to perform simple computer actions, such as typing.

2 RELATED WORK

One major problem when dealing with computer vision is improving the accuracy of a gesture that is unreliable when

dealing with different environments, such as the camera angle or lighting.

2.1 Haddad et al.

The paper used an uncertainty-aware prediction network trained on IMU data to obtain predictions that improved gesture recognition accuracy, to which they compared their methods to others and found that theirs were consistently higher and more accurate.

2.2 Tian et al.

The paper proposes a model of hand-object interaction that generates the hand and object while calculating the probability of the pose to better depict the real gesture. It performs data with other generation methods such as GrabNet and DexGraspNet that validate the effectiveness of the of the model by performing ablations on Object Pose Approximation (OPA), Scale Alignment (SA), and the HaMeR Prior (HP). The effectiveness is lessened by hand interference, such as misalignment.

2.3 Indriani et al.

A machine learning model using MediaPipe was created to detect ten gestures by determining the landmarks of the hand and if the fingers / hand were open or not. The model using Kinect achieved an accuracy 95% that caused a slight decrease in accuracy due to the imperfectness of the image it captured.

3 APPROACH

Many people used their own AI generated model to attempt to make an improved model with better accuracy. In this approach, we will use Google's basic gesture recognition model to detect simple gestures and Google's Colab to use their large amounts of free CPU power and a helpful Python environment [1]. This model from MediaPipe can recognize seven different gestures in either one or both hands and is the default model trained by Google. Through this model, we can use it to draw landmarks on hands to detect the type of gesture in the picture with an accuracy given for it as well.

Project source code available at <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1bRF7N9LgKpPGRMTfKxhT1GULiL9qWOM?usp=sharing>

Figure 1: (left) A drawn figure with low accuracy; (center) a drawn figure with an incorrect reading; (right) a drawn figure with high accuracy

4 EXPERIMENTS

We import `mediapipe`, `matplotlib`, `IPython.display`, `google.colab.output`, and `mediaPipe`'s gesture recognition model. First, we used `colab`'s capture video script in order to get the image from the camera. Then, that image is fed through `mediapipe`'s model to draw the landmarks and determine the accuracy and the gesture. Lastly, we visualize the image through `mediaPipe`'s function that outputs the accuracy, gesture name, and picture with drawn landmarks on it using `matplotlib` (see Figure 1). Sometimes, this implementation would suddenly break due to importing `mediapipe` without the audio classifier or because there were no hands in the picture and returned a null value. Overall, easy gestures that were palm to the camera were easily recognized and could work.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A successful process was made through attaching `mediapipe`'s basic gesture recognition AI with `colab`'s capture video script. However, a way to use that data in order to interact with the computer has not been made, mostly due to the many errors that were made through importing `mediapipe` and it's way of detecting gestures that could possibly end up being null if no hand was found. Two hands would also not be possible, and the accuracy of the gestures is extremely low, and one would need to have the palm facing the camera to attain that high accuracy. We could improve this system by building our own AI in computer vision with better algorithms. This could then be added to websites to perform actions such as clicking or scrolling when using a live video instead of an image. Maybe better algorithms for object detection could be found in the near future.

5.1 Future Work

In the future, a better gesture recognition model could be trained that can detect a variety of gestures, such as those from ASL or American Sign Language with high accuracy. In order to do this, a vast amount of training and CPU power would be required. A way to connect the model to a live camera in `colab` would be beneficial for fast training. Ideally, there would be a way to connect these gestures to our daily lives for entertainment and ease.

REFERENCES

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